

THE PROBLEMS AND CHALLENGES OF ENGLISH TEACHERS IN KUPANG REGENCY IN IMPLEMENTING CURRICULUM 2013

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Abstract

The curriculum in Indonesia has changed in ten times, it was started from curriculum 1947 to curriculum 2013 which at the beginning of its launch gained many pros and cons from various circles. The purpose of curriculum 2013 is to produce a productive, creative, innovative and characteristic generation. Teacher activeness is needed in creating and growing various activities. From the results of the Program for International Student (PISA) tests and evaluation in 2015 the performance of Indonesian students is still relatively low. Mastery of English becomes a necessity for students in this globalization era. The implementation of curriculum 2013 in junior and senior high schools in Kupang district is not comprehensive or maximal. This research is a qualitative research that explains the various phenomena occurring in the field. Data obtained from observations and interviews covering the problems and challenges faced by English teachers. Researchers took 10 schools in junior high school level by involving 30 English teachers and also 5 school in senior high school level. Total sampling is 35 teachers consist of 30 teachers from senior and 5 teachers from junior high school. In addition, the facilities and infrastructure should be paid more attention from the local government.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The curriculum in Indonesia has changed in ten times. It was started from the curriculum 1947 to the curriculum 2013 which at the beginning of its launch gained many pros and cons from various circles. Curriculum change seems to be the answer of the turmoil on the condition in society. Curriculum changes affect the juridical and academic aspects. From the juridical aspect, the change of the curriculum is the mandate of the National Medium Term Development Plan in 2010-2014 of the education sector, as well as presidential instruction Number 1 in 2010 on the Implementation Acceleration of National Development Priorities. The completion of curriculum and active learning methods based on the nation cultural values to arrange the nation competitiveness.

The purpose of curriculum 2013 is to produce a productive, creative, innovative and characteristic students but the low curriculum requires a thorough handling because in the life of a nation education plays a very important role to ensure the survival of the state and nation and also a vehicle to improve and develop the quality of human resources. In the Law of Republic of Indonesia on National Education System Number 20 in 2003, Chapter I, article I verse 19, the curriculum is defined as a set of plans and arrangements concerning objectives, content and instructional materials. In addition, according to Trump and Miller (1973) that curriculum includes teaching and learning methods, how to evaluate pupils and the whole program,

changing teaching staff, guidance and counseling, supervision and administration and structural matters regarding time, as well as the possibility of choosing lesson materials and ways used as guidelines for the implementation of learning activities to achieve certain educational goals. Thus the curriculum is seen as a plan and arrangement and learning activities.

The success of curriculum 2013 has to be seen from several factors such as principal leadership, teacher creativity, student activities, socialization, facilities and learning resources, a conducive academic environment and school community participation. If these things are considered, then the education purpose namely the freedom to educate the all of national students life without the influence of others for the sake of democracy through participatory democracy could be achieved. The implementation of curriculum 2013 is the actualization of curriculum in learning and the formation of competence and learners character. Teacher activeness is needed in creating and growing various activities in accordance with the plan that has been programmed. Saylor (1981) in Mulyasa (2002) says that "instructional is thus the implementation of curriculum plan, usually but not necessarily, involving teaching in the sense of students, teachers interaction in an educational setting. Teachers should learn the principles of learning, selection and the use of instructional media, the selection and the use of learning methods, the skills of assessing learners learning outcomes, and selecting and using learning strategies or approaches. These competencies are integral to a professional workforce, which could only be mastered well through the intensive practice experience. The three important aspects that have a very complex nature to be realized by teachers are pedagogical, psychological and didactic aspects simultaneously. The pedagogical aspect points to the fact that learning takes place in an educational environment.

Therefore, the teacher should accompany the learners to get the success of learning or the mastery of the particular competence. The psychological aspect refers to the fact that learners generally have different stages of development, which require different materials. In addition, the psychological aspects point to the fact that the learning process itself contains many variations, such as learning skills, motor skills, learning concepts and learning attitudes (Gagne 1984). These differences require different learning according to the type of learning that is taking place. Didactic aspects of teacher learning settings by teachers. In this case the teachers should determine in detail the particular type in learning process which saving in mind the basic competencies to be achieved. Fun and meaningful learning could be designed by each teacher with the following procedures: (1) warming and appreciation need to be done to explore learners knowledge, motivate learners by singing interesting material, and encourage them to learn new things. This warming and appreciation could be done by learning procedures starting with things that are known and understood, learners motivated by learning materials that are interesting and useful for their live, learners are moved to be interested and eager to know new things. (2) exploration is the stage of learning activities to introduce materials and relate them to the knowledge that students already have. Some of these could be practiced by introducing the basic materials and basic competencies that should be possessed by the learners, the relevance of standard materials and new basic competencies to the knowledge and competencies that mastered by learners and as educators they should have appropriate methods and use varies to increase student acceptance of new standard competence materials. (3) consolidation of learning is an activity to enable learners in the formation of competence and character, and connect with learners. Consolidation of learning could be executed by the procedure that involves learners actively in interpreting and understanding new materials and competencies, involving learners

actively in the process of solving the problems, especially in the actual problems of emphasis on structural linkages, which dealing between standard materials and new competencies with various aspects of activities within the community, and choose the most appropriate method so that the standard material could be processed into the competence and character of learners. Facts in the field that are obtained about unpreparedness of teachers. If every time a curriculum change requires massive training to the teacher, there is something wrong with the teacher's mindset over the course of the curriculum. The unpreparedness of the teachers is not only related to the affairs of the compensation, but related to his creativity problem, which is also caused by the formulation of a slow curriculum to be socialized by the government. In fact, teachers who are in charge of the area and the hinterland whether civil servant teachers, contracts or honorary staff would find difficult to follow the new things in a short time using an integrative thematic approach where takes many time to understand.

Curriculum 2013 based on character and competence want to change the education from the orientation towards the result and educational material as a process through the integrative thematic approach and contextual learning and learning (CTL). In order to succeed in implementing curriculum 2013, it would be wise for teachers to follow and understand the concept of curriculum 2013 in learning, to take creative initiative to understand other teachers in their schools so that they could support the successful implementation of curriculum 2013.

As a professional teacher, in carrying out the main tasks and functions need to pay attention to the principle of the profession. Principles of teacher profession are regulated in Law no. 14 in 2005 on Teachers and Lecturers Profession. In Chapter III, Article seven (7), in Verse 1 is argued that the profession of teachers and professors is a special field of work performed on the following principles: (1) should have talents, interests, calling souls and ideals, (2) being committed to improving the quality of education, (3) should have academic qualifications and background in accordance with the field of duty, (4) should have the necessary competencies in accordance with the task field, (5) should have the competence as a professional teacher, (6) earn income that determined in accordance with work performance, (7) should have the opportunity to develop the professionalism in a sustainable manner with lifelong learning, (8) should have the legal protection and run the professional duties, (9) should have the professional organizations that have the authority to regulate matters relating to professional duties.

The statement of Mohammad Nuh who ever served as Minister of Education and Culture on various occasions emphasized the need of change and development in curriculum 2013. Nuh Stated that the change and development of curriculum are a very important issue because the curriculum should always be adapted to the demands of the times. The need for change and development of curriculum 2013 is driven by several international studies on the ability of Indonesian learners in the international scene. The Program for International Student (PISA) test and survey results, which in 2015 involved 540,000 students in 70 countries, were analyzed carefully and complete so the survey and the test could obtain in the end of the next year. Through the address of <https://www.oecd.org/pisa/> of Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) data abundantly relating to PISA test and survey results can be gained. In tests and surveys of PISA 2015 data obtained that Singapore is the country that obtained the first rank for the third science material, reading, and math.

From the results of PISA tests and evaluation in 2015 the performance of Indonesian students is still relatively low. Successively average achievement scores of Indonesian students

for science, reading, and math are ranked 62, 61, and 63 of the 69 countries evaluated. The ratings and average Indonesian score do not differ greatly from previous PISA test results and surveys in 2012 which getting low scores in the third material, science, reading and mathematics.

In this survey data involves students aged 15-16 years, viewed from the presentation of Indonesia is still under the special in three abilities namely the ability of mathematics, reading ability and scientific ability (science) that reflects the education system in their respective countries. Mastering English becomes a necessity for students in this age of globalization. Junior High School (SMP) and Senior High School (SMA) students should be able to learn English, because English is not as bad as used in the school environment but English would help students to get to know the world widely. The Government of Indonesia issues: Laws of National Education (2003: 15) that "Foreign languages could be used as the language of instruction in certain educational units to support the ability of foreign language learners. That is one of the most important reasons why we should learn English in school. In accordance with curriculum 2013, learning management should emphasize more on student needs. Therefore, the results achievement of curriculum competency standards (SKL) is more realistic than the learning process that can be identified so that could be given the appropriate management action related to the English language learning in curriculum 2013. However, from the data gained in field that students are not be the center and the effect of leaning processing is not comprehensive or maximal in implementing of curriculum 2013 in junior and senior high schools in Kupang. The various needs of students dealing with the applying curriculum 2013 in the field cannot be identified normally because it is still a debate and rejection at the national level. Similarly, with the fact in the management of English language learning is still a lot of problems faced by teachers both in planning, implementation, and assessment. This is also due to the government policy on process standards and assessment standards that often change. Although not a few problems and obstacles faced by teachers in implementing the learning curriculum 2013. Creativity of teachers is needed in the process of learning in the classroom.

2. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research using a qualitative research that would explain the various phenomena that occur in the field. Research is obtained through participatory observation in the life of the participant (Sutama, 2012: 32). Qualitative research is also known as descriptive research. Descriptive research is a study that aims to describe a state or phenomena as it is, no manipulation or a particular treatment of the object of research (Sutama, 2012: 38). Data obtained from observations and interviews covering the problems and challenges faced by English teachers especially in junior and senior high schools in Kupang regency. The territory of Kupang regency is geographically located at the coordinate point 9°19' - 10°57' South Latitude and 121°30' - 124°11' East Longitude with a land altitude of sea level ranging from 0 to 500 meters. Condition of the surface of Kupang district is generally hilly, mountainous and partly of lowland with average slope of 45°. Kupang Regency as a whole consists of 24 Districts with a total of 310,573 people who generally live as farmers (Central Bureau of Statistics, Kupang regency 2012). In the education sector, Kupang regency has provided schools from junior high school level with 81 schools with a total of 1,126 teachers, while at the high school level there are 28 schools, but there are some sub-districts that do not have high school so that access to education services has not been fully absorbed by participants educate. The number of high

school teachers scattered in the district of Kupang only amounted to 300 teachers. As for English language teachers in SMP are 243 and in SMA there are 67 English teachers. Data is obtained from Regency education office of Kupang. Researchers took 5 schools in junior high school level by involving 10 English teachers and also 5 high school schools in the district with the number of teachers taken as many as 10 teachers so that the total sampling is 20 teachers in Kupang district consisting of junior and senior high school level.

Some phenomena which become the challenges and problems in almost all schools that located in Kupang regency in implementing K13 by teachers consisting of (1) in teaching and learning process, most of the challenges of teachers in general and especially for junior and senior high school that happened in the field of English language in Kupang Regency are still using the Education Unit Level Curriculum (KTSP) in teaching and learning process, they cannot move to K13, (2) teachers do not know their role, many teachers in Kupang regency who teach are not in accordance with their background so many of them asking what to teach and how to teach properly, (3) lacking and barely preparing lesson plan, this resulted that many teachers still using the copy paste system and in the end of learning process nothing was achieved, (4) improper learning methods, lack of tactics, techniques and methods in learning so that students tend to get bored and eventually they do not understand the material distributed by the teacher, (5) not all teachers have participated in the K13 training, (6) teachers who take part in training are the same teacher but it is difficult even unable to share the obtained knowledge from the training results due to limit the understanding and age factors, (7) some complaints from the teacher where, the teachers w too charged about administrative problems that were done by themselves finally their time was confiscated so that they could not arrange the lesson plan, (8) limited facilities (learning media, library, laboratory and electricity). And also the phenomenon or challenges of education that occur beside the concept of teachers understanding in implementing curriculum 2013 that still low. Educational challenges in Indonesia in general and especially in the area of education that occurred in Indonesia where during this disparity between quality "education city" and "education village "caused by the limited infrastructure and educational superstructure. Casually it also influences the quality of political participation of urban and rural communities. In connection with the gaps above related to curriculum 2013 where teachers are required to provide quality education professionally but on the other hand new problems arise as challenges when teachers do not have the material skills to have access and information networks such as TV, books, magazines, Newspapers and the internet to improve their professionals while enriching information about the development of knowledge and various dynamics of global life, so it is very difficult to imagine teachers can appear more professional and have the moral responsibility of the profession as a consequence in this global era.

3. CONCLUSION

The role of teachers is needed in the process of curriculum implementation in each school. Relating with the implementation of Curriculum 2013, teachers are not only being the spearhead of education and learning, but are the key to overall success. In order to succeed in implementing curriculum 2013, it would be wise for teachers to follow and understand the concept of curriculum 2013 in learning, to take creative initiative to understand other teachers in their schools so that they could support the successful implementation of curriculum 2013. In order to the implementation of curriculum 2013 in the field runs well and can gain the good

result, teachers should have competencies that are expected to perform the role of duties and functions as professional and government teachers in this case the education office in the area or in the center can complement the facilities and infrastructure, teacher training is improved and teacher welfare so finally the teacher can run the professional role with supported by media and adequate technology.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Zulfikri Ana and Akhmad Supriyatna, "The Black and White of Curriculum 2013", Am Press and Pustaka Bina Putera, pp 45, Mei 2014
- [2] Loeloek Endah Poerwati and Sofan Amri, "Curriculum 2013; A Curriculum Structure Inovation in Supporting the Fuuture", Prestasi Pustakaraya, pp 21, Februari 2013
- [3] Loeloek Endah Poerwati and Sofan Amri, "Curriculum 2013; A Curriculum Structure Inovation in Supporting the Fuuture", Prestasi Pustakaraya, pp 3, Februari 2013
- [4] H. E. Mulyasa, "The Development and Implementation of Curriculum 2013", PT. Remaja Rosdakarya, pp 24, Februari 2014
- [5] Hazrul Iswadi, "a little Pisa results was newly released in 2015", Article Draft, Surabaya University, 2014

